

A NOTE ON THE ACTION OF NITROSYL CHLORIDE ON MONOBROMOMALONAMIDES.

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The action of nitrosyl chloride on substituted malonamides, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CONHR})_2$, leads to $\text{HO}\cdot\text{N} : \text{C}(\text{CONHR})_2$ which give characteristic alkali and iron salts (Whitely, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 24). Bromo-malonamides of the type $\text{CHBr}(\text{CONHR})_2$ were expected to yield nitroso compounds, $\text{C}(\text{NO})\text{Br}(\text{CONHR})_2$ by the action of nitrosyl chloride. Contrary to these expectations compounds of the type $\text{ClBrC}(\text{CONHR})_2$ were obtained. The same compounds are obtained by the action of the usual chlorinating agent, sulphuryl chloride, on monobromomalonamides. That nitrosyl chloride may behave in this manner is not unknown (Solonia, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, **30**, 431).

Reaction of Nitrosyl Chloride and Monobromomalon-di-p-toluidide.—The amide (5 g.) suspended in benzene (150 c c.) was saturated with dry gaseous nitrosyl chloride at 0° . At the end of one hour the major portion of the amide went into solution which assumed a dark red colour. The mixture was then heated under reflux till the condensed vapour became colourless. The benzene solution was then filtered hot and concentrated. The substance, thus obtained, was collected, washed with light petroleum and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 135° . (Found: N, 7.04; Halogen, 29.11. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{ClBr}$ requires N, 7.08; Halogen, 29.2 per cent).

Reaction of Nitrosyl Chloride and Monobromomalon-dibenzylamide.—The reaction was carried out as above. The product after recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 153° . (Found: N, 7.32; Halogen, 29.2. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{ClBr}$ requires N, 7.08; Halogen, 29.2 per cent).

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